

INNOVATIVE PROCESS LINE FOR MATERIAL SAMPLE PREPARATION

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ABSTRACT. The successful establishment and sustainable development of mining enterprises depends on a number of factors, including geological research, management of mineral extraction and processing processes, and sample preparation technology. The sample preparation plants that are currently used have a multi-stage technological process, often with manual transfer of material between technological operations. Standard crushing and grinding equipment with a low degree of grinding, high metal consumption and overall dimensions is used. Separation of material by size also occurs on standard screens, which are poorly suited for sample preparation. The purpose of the work is to substantiate an innovative technological scheme for preparing mineral samples for laboratory analysis. The determining unit of the production line is a vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber, which has a degree of material grinding of more than 100 and allows one to obtain a final product with a particle size of -1 mm in one pass in an open crushing cycle, which reduces the number of overload devices that significantly affect sample clogging with material. Horizontal loading of the source material and unloading of the crushed material makes it possible to arrange all equipment in a horizontal plane, eliminate large-sized metal structures and ensure ease of maintenance. The vibrating screen of the improved design has a complex working profile, which provides a significant increase in the path of transportation of material particles along the sieving surface compared to its length, effective cleaning of the mesh and its visual inspection through the transparent lid, which eliminates clogging of the material of the previous sample. The working surface is a set of sieve cards that allow quick replacement of the worn part of the screening surface. The technical characteristics of the equipment and the general view of a small-sized modular crushing and grinding plant are presented.

Key words: *mineral exploration sampling, sample preparation, vibrating jaw crusher, vibrating screen, accuracy of analyses*

Introduction

The successful establishment and sustainable development of mining enterprises significantly depend on geological works. These works comprise a complex integrated set of preparatory and research production processes, as well as the effective management of mining and mineral processing during the operation of the mining enterprise. Mineral exploration sampling is a source of information on the quality and technological properties of mineral raw materials, composition and structure of mineral bodies, properties of ores and host rocks, as well as allows to perform an economic evaluation of the deposit (Roonwal, 2018).

The mineral exploration sampling process involves three main stages: initial sample collection, sample processing, and sample examination. Each stage utilizes distinct methods, equipment, and technological assumptions, which can impact the reliability of the information obtained about the explored deposit (Omelchuk et al., 2017). At each stage, there are errors that contribute to the error of the results obtained. The structure of the resulting error is formed at all stages of work with the sample and therefore consists of sampling error, preparation error and sample analysis error (Mladetskyi et al., 2019). Possible errors (Abzalov, 2011) can be caused by segregation of material during unloading from sampling devices or conveyor belts, contamination of samples by improper preparation procedures, changes in chemical or physical characteristics of the material caused by its crushing, grinding, homogenization, sieving, mixing, filtering, drying, packaging and transportation, etc. Incomplete and unreliable information about minerals is the cause of distortion of the assessment of the quality of mineral deposits and the feasibility study for the construction of a mining and processing plant and the operation of a deposit. Therefore, improving the quality of work at any stage of the mineral exploration sampling process is an urgent task that reduces the overall error of the final result.

The aim of the work is to substantiate an innovative technological scheme of preparation of mineral samples for laboratory analysis. The most labour-intensive operation in sample processing is the crushing of the selected product. The material coarseness of the initial sample can be 100 mm, and the required coarseness of the laboratory sample is mainly 0.1...0.074 mm, which determines the crushing degree $i \geq 1000$.

As a consequence, the technological process of laboratory sample preparation is multistage and includes the operations of crushing, grinding, abrasion, separation, mixing, reduction in sample amount. At increased moisture content of the initial sample, the technological line includes a drying device. With minor differences it is defined by a typical scheme of the apparatus chain (Figure 1). Schemes may differ in initial size and amount of material, degree of crushing and equipment arrangement (Lazarieva, 2015), but have common main drawbacks: multistage technological process, use of standard equipment poorly adapted for sample preparation, low-efficiency reloading between technological operations, large size and metal consumption.

Analysis of the given technological scheme (Figure 1) for the initial size of the geological sample of 20-30 mm shows a large amount of equipment, requiring a variety of binding links and creating conditions for contamination of the processed material with residues from the crushing of the previous sample. As the coarseness of the original sample increases, the number of crushing stages and the likelihood of contamination increases. In the process of material reloading between the equipment, when using manual labour, material losses are possible, which affects the reliability of analytical results. Widely used standard crushing and grinding equipment has a low degree of crushing and is inefficient, and the use of roller crushers is limited by the strength of the crushed rock.

A review of the literature on crushing and grinding equipment used in sample preparation is presented in a previous paper by the authors (Fedoskina, 2023). The raw sample is initially crushed mainly in jaw crushers with relatively

low speed of force loading (Korman et al., 2015). The height difference between the loading and unloading windows is more than 500...1000 mm. Considering the need for vertical loading and unloading of material, the loading window is located at a height requiring the installation of a feeding device in the form of a conveyor, elevator, etc. These mechanisms are difficult to clean, and in the process of transportation there may be a loss of bulk material.

Fig. 1. Typical sample preparation scheme

Most of the crushers are produced with one moving jaw, in particular, the widely used in sample preparation crushers with simple jaw motion. Terminator Jaw Crusher (TM Engineering) and Essa JC2501 (FLSmidth Essa) have almost the same technological parameters with some design differences. The crushing degree is $i \leq 50$, initial coarseness is up to 110 mm. Crushers with complex jaw motion manufactured by Retsch GmbH have elliptical jaw motion, which allows, in addition to compression, to apply shear loads to the material. This design solution allows to crush viscous raw materials, increases the crushing degree, gives a more even granulometric composition of the finished product, but has a serious negative effect in sample preparation – the significant abrasion of the working surfaces of the jaws contaminates the sample material with removed metal, affecting the reliability of analytical studies. The Rocklabs BOYD (Scott Rocklabs) Elite jaw crusher is designed with two movable jaws and separate drives in the feeding and unloading parts of the crushing chamber. This design scheme increases the jaw stroke in the loading zone, equalizes the force loading of the material over the height of the crushing chamber, but the relative displacement of the working surfaces of the jaws increases the wear of the metal, and the crushing degree $i \geq 25$ is not sufficient for sample preparation in one crushing stage.

After jaw crushers, which can form several crushing stages, roller crushers with a roller diameter of 200...250 mm and different initial coarseness are mainly used to obtain a sample size of -1 mm (Allen, 2009; Biletsky et al, 2019). The LMRC100

Roll Crusher (LAARMANN) has a maximum feed size of 30 mm. The SIEBTECHNIK WS 250 x 150 L double roll crusher accepts 12 mm material and the Lab Roll Crusher operates at an initial material size of -10 mm. The two-roll crushers used in sample preparation, operating on the principle of crushing the material, are inefficient because they have low crushing degrees ($i = 2...3$), limitations on crushing hard rocks, sticking of wet material on the rolls and their intensive wear (Sinha and Mukhopadhyay, 2016). In sample preparation, such shortcomings significantly affect the accuracy and reliability of sampling, which is of great importance in the control of technological processes of enrichment.

In various branches of industry, the use of vibrating jaw crushers is successfully increasing (Franchuk, 2010; Mazur, 2019). This class of machines provides impact character of load application to the crushed material and represents an oscillating system, in which the jaws are given oscillations with a frequency of 16 - 32 Hz (Shokhin, 2020; Altshul et al, 2021). Studies of crushers with pendulum motion of the cheeks and the lower axis of suspension are given in (Wolny, 2013; Sidor and Mazur, 2014; Mazur, 2017).

Methods and materials

Analysis of literature sources and existing technological schemes of sample preparation shows that the quality of sample preparation can be improved by reducing the stages of crushing, the number of storage, reloading and transporting devices, eliminating the loss of material during transportation, sticking of material on the working surfaces and their effective cleaning, as well as the possibility of creating a small-sized portable unit that provides sample preparation at the place of sampling.

On this basis, an innovative scheme of the technological process has been developed (Figure 2), including the hopper of the initial material 1, a vibrating feeder 2, a vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber 3, a vibrating screen 4, a vibrating abrasion machine 5.

Fig. 2. Innovative sample preparation scheme

In comparison with the existing schemes in the considered variant, a horizontal arrangement of the equipment is developed, which minimizes the presence of lifting and loading mechanisms between the units, improves the quality of cleaning of the working volume of the line and simplifies its maintenance.

The choice of vibration-impact method of applying load to the material, realized in the vibrating jaw crusher, allows to obtain a high degree of crushing (100 and more) and to combine in one unit the operations of crushing the initial material with a size ≤ 100 mm and grinding to a size ≤ 1 mm. This eliminates the multistage crushing and grinding operation, reduces the amount of equipment used and the probability of loss of sample material in the process of crushing and reloading.

Results and discussion

In order to tune the properties of the proposed new sample preparation scheme, studies are conducted on the dependence of abrasion time on the coarseness of the initial material. The abrasion of a sample of magnesite weighing 60 g in a vibrating abrasion machine is investigated and the results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Abrasion efficiency

Sample number	Size of the original, μm	Final particle size, μm	Abrasion time, s
1	1000-2500	100	365
2	500-1000	100	190
3	100 -500	100	118

The finished product of 0 -1 mm size (after the vibrating jaw crusher) contains a fairly large number of finely ground fractions, in particular, magnetite 0 - 500 microns more than 50 %. Taking into account two factors: abrasion time and granular composition of the crushed product, in the technological scheme a screen is used (number 4 in Figure 2), which allows to separate the product, providing a rational ratio of coarseness and abrasion time. The oversize product is fed into a vibrating jaw crusher for further crushing.

Realization of such a scheme can take place in the presence of highly efficient small-sized equipment. Experimental verification of the efficiency of the innovative technological scheme was carried out on separate laboratory samples of vibrating equipment, which conditionally modelled the sample preparation unit.

The vibrating feeder (Figure 3) includes a hopper 1, an eccentric vibrating exciter 2, a load-carrying element 3, elastic elements 4, a support frame 5.

Fig. 3. Vibrating feeder

The productivity of the vibrating feeder is regulated by the frequency of oscillation of the load-carrying element and reaches (when transporting sand) 1.5 t/h. The tray of the vibrating feeder is made in one piece with an oval transition of the bottom to the side walls and dimensions, mm: length 500, width 100, height 50, cantilever reach of the tray 250 mm. Such design of the vibrating feeder allows to qualitatively perform its cleaning with a brush after each worked sample.

In case of small sample volumes and lump sizes, loading can be carried out directly into the chute, which simplifies the subsequent cleaning of the feeder. The feed material is dosed by the vibrating feeder into the vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber

The crusher body 1 performs the function of the lower jaw, the suspension axis 2 of the upper jaw 3, a vibration exciter 4. The crusher is located on supporting shock absorbers 5, and the lower jaw 1 and the upper jaw 3 are connected by an elastic element 6. The drive shaft of the vibrating exciter is connected to the DC motor 8 by means of a petal clutch 9 (Figure 4), eliminating the impact of misalignment of rotating shafts on the performance of the crusher. The structural scheme of the crusher is presented in Figure 5 where the replaceable lining 7 on the working surfaces of the jaws is shown.

Fig. 5. Structural scheme of the crusher

This type of crushers has a high-frequency (16 - 32 Hz) impact character of load application to the crushed material and a large set of adjustable parameters that provide effective control of the process of material destruction (Fedoskina, 2018).

Material destruction occurs in the crushing chamber formed by the working surfaces of the jaws where the feed material entering the crusher receiving window is transported to the discharge slot and is subjected to high-frequency impact loading. Productivity of the crusher is up to 400 kg/h, essentially depending on the physical and mechanical properties of the material, its initial and final size. The effectiveness of the crusher in the mode of crushing geological samples is shown in the previous work of the authors (Fedoskina, 2023). The vibrating jaw crusher is the main unit of the technological scheme, which allows to provide samples' crushing in one stage due to high (more than 100) degree of crushing and horizontal

layout of the equipment. The technical characteristics of the crusher are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. *Technical characteristics of the crusher*

	Parameters and dimensions	
1	Receiving window size, mm	130 x 130
2	Height of discharge slot, mm	0 - 50
3	Crushing chamber length, mm	500
4	Lower jaw inclination angle, Rad	0 - 0.9
5	Frequency of jaw oscillation, Hz	0 -25
6	Dimensions, mm	
	length	1000
	width	600
	height	1200
7	Weight, kg	1200

The crushed material can undergo screening on a small-size screen with a complex profile of the screening surface. The screen (Figure 6) includes a box 1, mounted by means of elastic elements 2 on a support frame 3. In the oscillating motion of the box it is driven by a vibration exciter 4.

The vibrating screen has a complex working profile, which gives a significant increase in the transportation path of the material particles along the screening surface in comparison to its length, effective cleaning of the mesh and its visual control through a transparent cover.

Fig. 6. **Vibrating screen**

The screening surface is made of a set of cards, which allows to perform a quick replacement of the worn part of the cloth or installation of screens with holes. The technical characteristics of the screen are given in Table 3.

Loading and unloading spigots are located in the end or side surface of the box, providing horizontal multivariant docking with adjacent equipment.

Screening efficiency was investigated for magnetite of initial size -5 mm with a screening surface opening of 0.75 mm. The results are presented in Table 4.

The obtained results show a fairly high screening efficiency slightly decreasing with increasing productivity.

The conducted research proving the feasibility of the innovative technological scheme has shown the reality of creating a portable small-size sample preparation unit, the model of which is presented in Figure 7.

Table 3. *Technical characteristics of the screen*

	Parameters and dimensions	
1	Number of screens	1
2	Max. lump size in feed, mm	5
3	Min. screening size, mm	0.1
4	Screen area, m ²	0.3
5	Vibration amplitude, mm	3
6	Oscillation frequency, Hz	17
7	Dimensions, mm	
	Length	1200
	Width	400
	Height	1000
8	Weight, kg	100

Table 4. *Screening efficiency*

Q, kg/h	E, %
290	95.93
670	94.45
805	93.89

Fig. 7. **Small-sized modular crushing and grinding plant**

The modular plant accepts material pieces of up to 130 mm, which are crushed in a vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber to a size of -1 mm and fed to a vibrating screen for screening. The material crushed to a fraction of -1 mm sample is further refined according to known methods and the sample is transferred for analysis.

Approximate dimensions of the installation are: length – 3000 mm, width - 800 mm, height - 1700 mm.

The plant equipment is assembled on a single support frame, which does not require a special powerful foundation and is fixed to the mounting surface with anchor bolts.

Horizontal arrangement of loading and unloading spigots and their flexible connection makes it possible to use each unit separately by opening the docking connection. Placement of the small-sized modular crushing and grinding unit at the sampling site will significantly reduce labour costs for packing and moving the selected geological material to the laboratory for analysis.

Conclusions

1. An innovative technological scheme has been developed, based on the efficiency of vibration equipment, ensuring a single-stage technological process of sample preparation, which predetermines an increase in the quality of the field testing results.

2. The sample preparation, according to the considered technological scheme, is based on three main small-sized units (vibrating crusher, vibrating screen, vibrating abrasion machine), functionally replacing a set of old equipment, which does not meet modern requirements, has a low degree of crushing, large size, metal consumption, and imperfection of docking inter-unit units.

3. In the proposed new sample preparation scheme, the design features of the equipment allow for the installation of the sample preparation unit at the zero level of the assembly site, eliminating the use of multi-level metal structures, which ensures convenience and ease of maintenance of the units and improves the quality of cleaning of the working parts from possible residues of the crushed sample material.

4. Studies of laboratory samples of equipment: vibrating feeder, vibrating jaw crusher, vibrating screen, included in the innovative technological scheme, showed their high efficiency in sample preparation, the possibility of simple and reliable connection, eliminating losses of material in the process of reloading.

5. On the basis of laboratory samples, the model of a modular crushing and grinding plant has been developed for crushing brittle rocks of any strength, with an initial size of up to 130 mm and a crushing degree of more than 100, with a horizontal equipment layout with one crushing stage, accessibility for high-quality cleaning of elements, ease of installation and relocation to another site.

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